

	Comp.1	Comp.2	Comp.3	Comp.4	Comp.5	Comp.6
bio1	0.02356182	0.02615522	0.36800119	0.08411901	0.06847758	0.03618468
bio2	0.00123455	0.0211862	0.0831205	0.00372012	-0.000474	0.02927379
bio3	0.00351841	-0.0023374	0.01830121	0.00683699	-0.000704	0.02532773
bio4	-0.9938472	-0.0793524	0.06030604	0.02042028	0.00354904	-0.0137635
bio5	0.01011385	0.03415058	0.39155444	0.10337571	0.04447229	-0.0026464
bio6	0.03570761	0.01632048	0.30292132	0.11282079	0.06933313	-0.008348
bio7	-0.0255938	0.0178301	0.08863312	-0.0094451	-0.0248608	0.00570164
bio8	0.01015287	0.0062987	0.36483464	-0.0300813	0.08309703	0.42096751
bio9	0.03367247	0.04450769	0.35593972	0.23828253	0.05427495	-0.4702339
bio10	0.01078826	0.02459887	0.35167478	0.08845878	0.05872365	0.01891671
bio11	0.0360614	0.02663482	0.34471634	0.08659943	0.05529379	0.01877605
bio12	0.07314225	-0.8700702	0.00739251	0.08254261	0.15713631	-0.2642805
bio13	0.01223511	-0.1226185	0.09246193	-0.1338767	-0.2605299	0.03415474
bio14	0.0015047	-0.0322816	-0.0382118	0.05979902	0.1260263	-0.0283139
bio15	0.00121524	0.01638394	0.06778538	-0.0607359	-0.1111672	0.08502747
bio16	0.03261635	-0.3387484	0.21354062	-0.3244985	-0.619474	0.04221161
bio17	0.0056021	-0.110835	-0.1214594	0.19919281	0.40617473	-0.0924879
bio18	0.01233775	-0.2154063	0.07161107	-0.4433743	0.50303123	0.46457708
bio19	0.01618194	-0.2016838	-0.1353567	0.72275546	-0.221276	0.54096196
Standard dev	5232.36408	646.098656	2.12E+02	1.69E+02	1.18E+02	7.47E+01
Proportion of	0.9814257	0.0149644	1.60E-03	1.02E-03	5.01E-04	2.00E-04
Cumulative F	0.9814257	0.9963901	9.98E-01	9.99E-01	1.00E+00	1.00E+00

Comp.14	Comp.15	Comp.16	Comp.17	Comp.18	Comp.19
0.56094135	0.10004814	0.61811076	0.08480663	0.19266922	1.12E-07
0.29290528	-0.5337656	-0.0242635	0.01914742	-0.073194	-1.97E-08
0.0410418	0.76344281	0.04878326	-0.0020502	-0.0302886	-1.52E-07
0.00954339	-0.0071452	-0.0047414	0.00030068	0.01504096	-2.95E-10
-0.5738978	-0.0012062	0.15403683	0.01181068	0.05499799	-0.5773503
-0.3628049	-0.2289785	0.17096778	0.02482973	0.00095664	0.57735024
-0.211093	0.22777238	-0.0169311	-0.0130191	0.05404114	0.5773503
-0.0298688	-0.0328715	0.0008216	0.00408103	-0.0065408	1.14E-08
0.00111205	0.01736826	0.00135408	0.00410513	-0.0038625	3.17E-09
0.19472205	0.09585872	-0.3081171	-0.0624904	-0.7973438	-1.02E-07
0.20014196	0.0533384	-0.6711292	-0.0704738	0.55999896	1.86E-08
0.00739894	-0.0225429	-0.0026393	0.00985706	-0.0001945	-3.93E-10
0.01667224	-0.0083042	-0.0025201	0.0234539	0.01634449	5.47E-09
-0.0183334	0.03140421	-0.1183106	0.93930509	-0.0241071	1.27E-08
-0.1070979	-0.0413975	0.02214758	-0.0062422	-0.0018565	4.32E-09
0.0004145	0.0220412	0.00693662	-0.0206626	-0.0075939	-4.29E-09
-0.007613	0.02252978	0.04192318	-0.3149553	0.01015802	-4.04E-09
-0.0338291	0.01303451	-0.0055096	-0.0010044	0.0015783	1.28E-09
-0.004623	0.00439987	-0.0037062	0.00110296	0.00164289	-6.37E-10
6.78E+00	5.09E+00	3.31E+00	2.89E+00	1.73E+00	0
1.65E-06	9.28E-07	3.94E-07	2.99E-07	1.08E-07	0
1.00E+00	1.00E+00	1.00E+00	1.00E+00	1.00E+00	1